

Hydrotalcite-zeolite composites as precursors for catalysis: Synthesis, transformation and structural stability

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ABSTRACT

In this study, Cu-based hydrotalcite-zeolite (CuHT-ZSM-5) composites were synthesized and characterized to explore their potential as catalyst precursors. The hydrotalcite phase was successfully formed on ZSM-5 zeolite supports with different Si/Al ratios under standard co-precipitation conditions (pH = 10, T = 65 °C). Structural analysis confirmed that the zeolite framework remained intact during synthesis, with only minor acidity modifications observed for Al-containing ZSM-5. The hydrotalcite layers were composed of copper, magnesium and aluminium cations, while the carbonate anions were used as interlayer anions.

Thermal decomposition of the CuHT phase resulted in in-situ generation of highly dispersed mixed metal oxides (MMOs). Textural characterization revealed that optimal calcination temperatures (500–600 °C) allow to obtain materials with high specific surface areas, while excessive heating (≥ 800 °C) led to partial collapse of the porous structure and formation of new MgSiO₃ phases.

The study demonstrates that CuHT-ZSM-5 composites are structurally stable, thermally resistant, and exhibit tuneable acidity – key properties for catalytic applications. These findings open new possibilities for optimizing MMO-zeolite catalysts, particularly for NH₃-SCO reactions.

1. Introduction

The nowadays catalysis requires materials that allow achieving high activity and the formation of targeted products at specific temperature window, without generation of undesired, secondary pollutants. One of materials that gain more and more interest are supported and unsupported transition metal oxides, e.g. copper oxides. Such materials are reported to be efficient in numerous processes like volatile organic compounds combustion [1,2], water gas shift reaction (WGS) [3] or selective catalytic reduction of nitric oxide (NO_x SCR) [4–6]. The performance of these catalysts is strongly influenced by their composition, structural properties and dispersion of active phases. Our scientific interest related to copper-based catalysts includes the potential application of these materials in ammonia oxidation process (NH₃-SCO), a process that allows conversion of ammonia into environmentally

friendly nitrogen (N₂) [7].

One of major challenges in the NH₃-SCO, is to achieve high catalytic activity and selectivity to N₂ at temperatures up to 350–400 °C. Our previous research showed that copper oxides (CuO) supported on Mg-Al-oxide materials exhibit promising activity for NH₃-SCO, with reaction selectivity being particularly sensitive to CuO dispersion [8–12]. Increasing copper loading enhances NH₃ conversion; however, it also promotes formation of bulk-like CuO, which reduces the specific surface area (SSA) and decreases selectivity toward N₂. These findings highlight the need to carefully balance catalyst composition and morphology to optimize performance.

To address these challenges, we devised a strategy to develop composite catalysts that integrate/combine Cu-mixed metal oxides (Cu-MMO), as the active component with zeolites as supporting materials. The MMOs and zeolites represent two distinct classes of catalytic

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materials with complementary properties. The MMOs offer significant flexibility in surface functionality, as their catalytic behaviour can be adjusted by modifying metal composition and loading [13]. This versatility also presents challenges, as metal dispersion and synthesis method critically affect the final properties of the catalysts [14]. Thus, the synthesis and post-synthesis processes, as well as support selection and treatment require special care to obtain the materials with the desired properties. Formation of unintended metal oxide phases can negatively affect catalytic performance, surface area and porosity.

Zeolites, on the other hand, are characterized by a well-defined, highly developed porous structure, and exhibit higher specific surface area (270–350 m²/g) [6,15,16] in comparison with mixed metal oxides (15–150 m²/g) [8,9]. However, post-synthetic modifications, such as impregnation, can lead to pore blockage, reducing the accessibility of active sites and alter the acidic properties of zeolite framework [17,18]. Therefore, our idea is to use the zeolite materials as effective structural supports that will enhance MMO dispersion, improve catalytic efficiency and mitigate the limitations associated with the MMOs such as low surface area and pore blockage. By combining these materials into composite systems, we aim to create a unique structure that retain the advantages of both components (feasibility of metal loading – MMO, high surface area and well-developed porosity – zeolites) while overcome their drawbacks (low surface area and formation of bulk-like species – MMO).

Our current research focuses on developing optimized synthesis strategies for these composite materials and refining post-synthesis treatment. As the precursors of mixed metal oxides, we have selected hydrotalcite-like materials (HT), which can incorporate various di- and tri-valent cations in different ratios (typically $M^{3+}/(M^{2+} + M^{3+}) = 0.15\text{--}0.33$ [19]). Upon calcination, HT materials transform into simple or complex oxide systems depending on their chemical composition and the applied temperature [11]. To achieve our objectives, we aim to synthesize the desired HT material using a one-pot process in the presence of zeolite. However, the synthesis conditions must be set in that way the HT structure is formed without zeolite structure damages. The subsequent calcination treatment is designed to facilitate the in-situ generation of mixed metal oxides on the zeolite surface.

As the support material, we have selected the commercially available ZSM-5 structures with varying Si/Al ratios. The calcination of HTs on ZSM-5 is expected to result in homogenous dispersion of oxides across the zeolite surface. However, this process might partially block pores or influence the stability of zeolite framework (porous structure), potentially reducing surface area and accessibility. While these effects must be carefully managed, our primary goal is to maximize the exposure of MMO active sites while preserving the structural integrity of the zeolite framework.

The combination of hydrotalcites with another type of materials opens wide possibilities of materials modification with huge potential in modern materials engineering. The successful synthesis of composites and hybrid HT materials combined with biochar [20], hydroxyapatite [21], melanin [22] and zeolites [23–25] has been previously reported, underscoring the potential of combining distinct materials in innovative designs. An overview of the composites of layered double hydroxide with zeolite was recently published by Velázquez-Herrera [26], however the most common application is for adsorption of contaminants from aqueous solution [27].

Calcined hydrotalcite-derived mixed oxides supported on zeolites have so far been reported mainly for adsorption-related environmental applications, such as CO₂ [28,29] and VOC [30] removal or for catalytic conversion and upgrading of biomass- and hydrocarbon-derived feedstocks, including cracking, pyrolysis and selective oxygenate transformations [31–34], while their direct use as catalysts in gas-phase flue-gas purification reactions remains scarcely explored [35].

[20–23] Since our idea was to connect the zeolites (as supports) and hydrotalcites (as precursors of active phase) in order to obtain the catalysts of high surface area and well dispersed active sites, the *in-situ*

transformation of hydrotalcites into MMOs represents more promising method of catalysts preparation in comparison to wet-impregnation or ion-exchange methods. In case of wet-impregnation and ion-exchange, the formation of big aggregates of CuO is more possible than in case of *in-situ* thermal decomposition of hydrotalcites, what might influence CuO accessibility and reducibility. Since both factors are recognized to be relevant in catalysis, the *in-situ* transformation of HT might be a good solution for receiving highly accessible supported copper oxides. Our goal is to develop and propose the optimized synthesis protocol for such composites. We believe that the anchoring of mixed metal oxides and zeolites is a key factor for enhancement of catalytic activity and selectivity in NH₃-SCO and NO_x SCR. As far as we know, such type of materials is not described in scientific literature. The MMO-zeolite catalysts could find application in wide range of catalytic approaches, due to the well-known flexibility in cations incorporation in hydrotalcite precursors and variability of zeolite supports. However, due to the possible problems with the materials synthesis and post-synthesis treatment, the procedure needs optimization and careful verification.

The synthesis procedure of new composites should cover the following aspects:

1. Determination of the stability of zeolite support under the hydrotalcite synthesis conditions.
2. Validation of the appropriate formation of hydrotalcite-like structures in presence of zeolite support.
3. Determination of thermal stability of composites to evaluate the optimal calcination temperature.
4. Characterisation of materials to confirm the presence of desired structures/active phases.

In this article, we present the synthesis pathway for ZSM-5 materials playing role of support for Cu-Mg-Al hydrotalcite. We have selected the zeolite of Si/Al ratio 11.5 and pure silica material where no Al is present. The goal of experiments was to determine the possible influence of Al present in ZSM-5 framework on the HT synthesis over the ZSM-5 surface and understanding the thermal treatment resulting into formation of MMO with high surface area and dispersed, accessible Cu oxide phase. We performed the materials characterisation to exclude the conditions that might result in framework degradation.

2. Material and methods

The hybrid catalysts, their precursors as well as reference samples were prepared. The idea is that mixed metal oxides containing Cu, Mg and Al will be obtained by the calcination of hydrotalcite-like materials that are considered as the precursor of MMO. MMO precursor (HT) is deposited by one pot synthesis on the support - ZSM-5 material. Cu-oxides are considered as the active phase/active centres, while the Mg and Al as the supporting metals for the appropriate development of MMO structure.

2.1. Chemicals

The zeolite materials with the theoretical Si/Al ratio of 11.5 and the pure Si material was purchased from Zeolyst International, USA. The copper nitrate (Cu(NO₃)₂•3H₂O; purity 99 %), magnesium nitrate (Mg(NO₃)₂•6H₂O, purity 99 %), aluminium nitrate (Al(NO₃)₃•9H₂O, purity 98 %), sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃, purity 99 %) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH, purity 98 %) were purchased from Penta Chemicals, the Czech Republic. All materials were used as supplied without further purification and all aqueous solutions were prepared using distilled water.

2.2. Zeolite support stability

The stability of each zeolite was tested under the conditions of HT synthesis. In these conditions, 2 g of support was dispersed in distilled

water with constant stirring. The slurry was heated up to 65 °C. After the stabilisation of temperature, the pH was established to 10. The dispersed zeolite was stirred for further 90 min. During the whole time of stability tests, the pH was checked and changes were recorder after each 5 min (first 30 min) and after each 15 min (till the end) of stirring. Simultaneously at each step approx. 5 ml of slurry was taken and filtered to separate the zeolite. The filtered materials were analysed in order to describe the possible changes occurring during the stirring. The ZSM-5 of Si/Al ratio 11.5 is labelled as ZSM, while the 100 % Si material (SiO₂) is labelled as ZSM(p).

2.3. Synthesis of MMO precursor

The hydrotalcite precursor was prepared under the standard synthesis conditions described in our previous works [8], however in current case the synthesis was performed as one pot synthesis in the presence of zeolite support. A water solution of Cu, Mg and Al nitrate salts with a molar concentration of 1.0 mol/L was added dropwise to the reactor containing the distilled water and the ZSM or ZSM(p) of liquid: solid weight ratio of 25:1. The vessel was pre-heated to 65 °C. The co-precipitation was performed at constant pH = 10 in presence of Na₂CO₃ solution (c = 0.5 mol/L) added dropwise together with the metal nitrates. The amounts of salts were calculated to obtain a M²⁺/M³⁺ molar ratio of 2.03, where the desired loading of metal cations was: Cu = 5 mol. %, Mg = 62 mol. % and Al = 33 mol. %. The obtained precipitate was aged at synthesis conditions (65 °C under atmospheric pressure) for 90 min. Obtained slurry was washed with distilled water and dried in an oven at 60 °C for 48 h. The amount of zeolite support was chosen to obtain the desired CuHT and ZSM-5 ratio of 1:1 and 2:1 (weight basis). Samples were labelled as: CuHT-ZSM_1:1, CuHT-ZSM(p)_1:1 and CuHT-ZSM_2:1, CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1, regarding the support used. A hydrotalcite with a composition of Cu = 5 mol. %, Mg = 62 mol. % and Al = 33 mol. % and a composite of zeolite with Mg = 67 mol. % and Al = 33 mol. % hydrotalcite (without Cu, labelled as HT) were also synthesized and used as references. The reference hydrotalcite was labelled as CuHT, while the reference composite materials as HT-ZSM_1:1 and HT-ZSM(p)_1:1.

2.4. Materials characterisation

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed using Rigaku SmartLab with use of Cu K α and Co K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.154$ nm and $\lambda = 0.179$ nm, respectively). The XRD patterns were evaluated using PDXL 2 software (v. 2.4.2.0, Rigaku) and compared with PDF-2 database (ICDD, Newton Square, USA, released 2015). The crystallite size was calculated using Debye-Scherrer equation: $L = (k\lambda)/(\beta\cos\theta)$ (k – shape factor (0.89), λ – X-ray wavelength Cu K α = 0.154 nm, β – line broadening at half of the maximum intensity (FWHM), θ – Bragg angle). Characteristic 2 Theta positions used for calculations: for HT: 12.5, 39.6, 71.3, 72.8° 2 Theta; Z: 8.5, 9.4, 16.4, 23, 23.5, 34° 2 Theta.

The NH₃ temperature programmed desorption (NH₃-TPD) was performed with use of AutoChemII 2920 (Micromeritics) connected on-line with a quadrupole mass spectrometer HPR-20EGA (Hiden Analytical). Before analysis the 0.04 g of sample was outgassed at 300 °C for 1 h in flow of He (50 ml/min) and saturated in flow of NH₃ (5 mol. % NH₃/He) at 75 °C for 100 min. After saturation the weakly adsorbed NH₃ was removed under the flow of He (50 ml/min) at same temperature. The TPD was registered in range of 75–700 °C (heating rate 20 °C/min) in flow of He (50 ml/min).

The chemical composition of samples was determined with the use of X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF, Spectro, Xepos, Ametek). The following K α energy lines were used for the determination of metals content: 1.740 keV (Si), 1.254 keV (Mg), 1.486 keV (Al) and 8.040 keV (Cu).

The thermogravimetric measurements coupled with mass spectroscopy analysis (TG-MS) were made using SetSys Evolution (Setaram) with

analysis of evolved gases using mass spectrometer QMG 700 (Pfeiffer). Experiments were carried out in alumina crucibles without standard in a dynamic atmosphere containing 20 mol. % O₂ and 80 mol. % Ar with the total flow rate of 40 ml/min. The sample mass was 34.04 mg for CuHT-ZSM 2:1 sample and 11.18 mg for CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1. The samples were equilibrated at 15 °C for 30 min and then were heated with a rate of 10 °C/min to 1000 °C. The released gases were detected based on the characteristic m/z signals: 28 and 44 for CO₂, 17 and 18 for H₂O, 30 and 46 for NO₂.

Low-temperature nitrogen adsorption was performed in a 3Flex Micromeritics sorptometer at temperature of –196 °C. Before measurements, samples were outgassed under vacuum at 350 °C for approx. 24 h. The specific surface area of samples was calculated based on the Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) method as well as modified Rouquerol approach, while the micropore volume and the external surface area were determined based on the t-plot method (following Broekhoff-De Boer standard isotherm). The $dV/d\log(w)$ pore volume distribution was established by the Barret-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method following the Broekhoff-De Boer isotherm with the Faas Correction.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed with use of Vega 4, Tescan. Images were collected with the accelerating voltage 30 keV using the backscattered electrons (BSE) and secondary electrons (SE) mode. Before analysis, samples were gold sputtered.

Temperature programmed reduction with use of hydrogen (H₂-TPR) was performed in an AutoChem II 2920 Micromeritics apparatus with the thermal conductivity detection (TCD). The results were collected in the temperature range of 40–600 °C with the isothermal hold up at 600 °C for 30 min. The profiles were registered with heating rate 10 °C/min in the flow of 10 mol.% H₂/Ar (30 ml/min). Before an experiment, samples (0.03 g) were outgassed in the flow of Ar (50 ml/min) at 500 °C for 1 h. The water vapor during the TPR measurement was captured in a cold-trap. For selected runs in order to check H₂O signal and presence of CO₂ and CO, cold-trap was bypassed and AutoChem device was connected online to quadrupole MS (Hiden Analytical, HPR-20 EGA); $m/z = 46, 44, 32, 30, 28, 18, 16$ and 2 were collected.

2.5. Catalytic test

Selective catalytic oxidation of ammonia was studied in a flow quartz reactor with inner diameter of 4 mm at the atmospheric pressure. Measurements were taken in the temperature range 375–275 °C with isothermal steps every 25 °C (150 min) and temperature rate 5 °C/min between steps. The inlet reaction gas mixture was composed of 350 ppm of NH₃ and 10 mol.% O₂ with nitrogen as balance, with total flow rate of 100 ml/min. Before experiments, samples (0.2 g of grain size ~ 0.160–0.350 mm) were activated in an air flow (100 ml/min) at 375 °C for 60 min.

Ammonia, water vapor and the reaction products, i.e. nitric oxide (NO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and nitrous oxide (N₂O), were detected by a FT-IR detector (Antaris IGS, Nicolet).

The ammonia conversion and nitrogen selectivity were calculated as follows:

$$(NH_3)_{conv} = \left(\frac{[NH_3]_{in} - [NH_3]_{out}}{[NH_3]_{in}} \right) \cdot 100 (\%)$$

where [NH₃]_{in} is inlet ammonia concentration, [NH₃]_{out} is outlet ammonia concentration at steady state.

$$(N_2)_{sel} = \left(1 - \frac{[NO]_{out} + [NO_2]_{out} + 2[N_2O]_{out}}{[NH_3]_{in} - [NH_3]_{out}} \right) \cdot 100 (\%)$$

where: (N₂)_{sel} is selectivity to dinitrogen, [NO]_{out}, [NO₂]_{out} and [N₂O]_{out} are outlet steady state concentrations of NO, NO₂ and N₂O, respectively.

The selectivity to side products was calculated using equation:

$$S_i = \frac{[i]_{out}^*}{\sum [i]_{out}^*} \cdot 100 (\%)$$

where: S_i is selectivity to the side-product i ; $[i]_{out}^*$ related to the molar amount of reacted NH_3 .

3. Results

3.1. Stability of ZSM-5 materials

The research focused on the desilication process [36–38], shows that the hydrothermal treatment of zeolites in NaOH solution in temperature up to 100 °C, might result in change of Si/Al ratio and the materials structure. The desilication conditions are close to the standard conditions of hydrothermal synthesis that we apply for composites preparation [8,11,39]. Since the destruction of ZSM-5 structure is not desired, the determination of the stability of zeolite ZSM-5 support is essential for the synthesis of hydrothermal-zeolite compounds. Stability of ZSM-5 materials during conditions of hydrothermal treatment stability was evaluated by assessing changes in phase structure and acidity.

The results of XRD analysis (Fig. S1, Supplementary) show the ZSM-5 structure after 30, 60 and 90 min of hydrothermal treatment. The observed diffraction peaks are characteristic for the MFI topology of ZSM-5 (ICDD PDF-2 cards: 00-042-0024 and 01-089-1421, Fig. S1A and Fig. S1B, respectively). The shape and the position of XRD peaks are the same for treated samples vs. the fresh ZSM and ZSM(p). The crystallite size of samples does not show significant changes regarding the raw, untreated materials (Fig. S1). Then it can be inferred that the structure of ZSM-5 does not change during hydrothermal treatment and that the Si/Al ratio of parent ZSM-5 does not impact the structure stability during the hydrothermal treatment.

Fig. 1. The NH_3 -TPD measurements of A. ZSM and B. ZSM(p) reference samples as fresh materials and after hydrothermal treatment (65 °C) under the pH = 10.

The NH_3 desorption curves of fresh and hydrothermally treated materials are presented in Fig. 1. The TPD profile of fresh ZSM shows occurrence of two desorption peaks that partly overlap (Fig. 1A). The peak around 225 °C is ascribed to weak acid sites, while the peak around 450 °C is associated with strong acid sites [40]. The hydrothermal treatment results in significant change of TPD profile. The ZSM sample after hydrothermal treatment shows the occurrence of a broad band around 250–320 °C without showing any maxima at the high-temperature region, what suggests the reduction in the number of acid sites, mainly strong acid sites. The total desorbed NH_3 amount decreases from 1.65 to 1.21 mmol/g after treatment, confirming the partial loss of acidity.

The comparison of NH_3 -TPD curves before and after treatment for ZSM(p) sample (Fig. 1B) does not show significant changes. Both curves show maximum at 250 °C in low-temperature desorption range and at 500 °C in high-temperature desorption range. The amount of desorbed NH_3 is comparable: 0.05 and 0.06 mmol/g for fresh sample and after treatment, respectively.

3.2. Characterisation of hydrothermal-zeolites composites

The idea of composite materials is to prepare a hydrothermal-zeolite of intended chemical composition (molar metal loading: Cu = 5 mol.%, Mg = 62 mol. % and Al = 33 mol. %) in presence of ZSM-5 zeolites with different Si/Al ratio. The synthesized unsupported Cu-MgAl hydrothermal-zeolite is considered as the reference sample for the validation of CuHT structure. The chemical composition of hydrothermal-zeolite was chosen based on our previous research, where we consider such materials as the precursors of active and selective catalysts for NH_3 -SCO [10,11,41].

The analysis of chemical composition (Table 1) confirms that the calculated weight ratio of HT and ZSM as well as the $\text{M}^{3+}/(\text{M}^{2+} + \text{M}^{3+})$ ratio are in line with the intended values. However, the XRF measurements of cation loading reveal that the Cu mol. % loading is higher than the expected values. The differences between the desired and actual values might result from the measurement error, partial dealumination or ion exchange during the synthesis [6].

The XRD patterns of composite materials and reference samples are shown in Fig. 2, while the calculations of the crystallite size and hydrothermal-zeolite cell parameters are summarized in Table 1 and Fig. 2.

The diffractograms of reference hydrothermal-zeolite, CuHT (Fig. 2), show characteristic patterns of hydrothermal-zeolite observed at $2\theta = 13, 27, 41, 46, 54, 72$ and 74° , that correspond to the hydrothermal-zeolite crystal planes: (003), (006), (012), (015), (018), (110) and (113), respectively [39,42]. The calculated cell parameters a and c , that refer to the distance between the cations in brucite-like layers (a) and to the interlayer distance (c) are typical for materials containing CO_3^{2-} as the interlayer anions [43] and cations of ionic radii close to Mg^{2+} .

In case of composite materials, the peaks corresponding to the hydrothermal-zeolite crystal planes (003), (012), (015), (110) and (113) are observed at the similar positions as for CuHT. The peaks of hydrothermal-zeolite and zeolites at $2\theta = 25\text{--}30^\circ$ are overlapped, thus the peak assigned to crystal plane (006) is not visible. However, the occurrence of other characteristic peaks and the calculations of a and c cell parameters (Table 1), confirm the formation of the desired structures. The comparison of both sets of compounds shows, that the different Si/Al ratio of the zeolite does not influence the formation of hydrothermal-zeolite like phase. However, it is worth noting that the a and c values calculated for ZSM(p) set are higher in comparison to ZSM set and this might be related to the Si/Al ratio. The calculated crystallite size of hydrothermal-zeolite (Table 1) is similar in comparison to the reference HT materials (Fig. 2).

The XRD patterns characteristic for MFI structure are clearly visible at the diffractograms and are at the same positions as the reference ZSM and ZSM(p) materials (Fig. 2). The comparison of the diffractograms of reference materials and the composites suggests, that the deposition of hydrothermal-zeolite on the zeolite does not result in a collapse of the zeolite framework. The crystallite size of zeolite phase calculated for

Table 1

The chemical analysis of composites. Int – intended values, Calc – calculated/real values.

Sample	HT/Z ^[a]		mol. % ^[b]			M ³⁺ /(M ²⁺ +M ³⁺) ^[b]		L (nm) ^[c]		HT cell (nm) ^[d]	
	Int	Calc	Cu	Mg	Al	Int	Calc	HT	Z	a	c
HT-ZSM_1:1	1	0.9	0	69	31	0.33	0.31	8	45	3.04	22.81
CuHT-ZSM_1:1	1	1.1	10	61	29	0.33	0.29	10	43	3.04	22.88
CuHT-ZSM_2:1	2	2.0	11	62	27	0.33	0.27	10	47	3.04	22.97
HT-ZSM(p)_1:1	1	1.1	0	72	28	0.33	0.28	8	49	3.07	24.52
CuHT-ZSM(p)_1:1	1	1.3	7	66	27	0.33	0.27	6	54	3.07	24.61
CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1	2	2.1	6	67	27	0.33	0.27	9	47	3.07	24.38

^[a] The Hydrotalcite/Zeolite weight ratio calculated based on XRF results. The zeolite content was calculated based on the reference ZSM and ZSM(p) chemical composition that are considered as reference samples. The HT and CuHT content were calculated after considering the zeolite related amount of Al and recalculation of results for HT and CuHT calculations.

^[b] The mol. % of metals calculated based on XRF results.

^[c] Crystallite size of HT - hydrotalcite and Z - zeolite calculated based on the XRD results.

^[d] Cell parameters *a* and *c* calculated based on the characteristic hydrotalcites patterns $d_{hkl} = (003)$ and $d_{hkl} = (110)$.

composites series ZSM is similar (around 45–47 nm) to the reference ZSM material (45 nm), while for samples set ZSM(p) it is lower as it is 47–54 nm in the composite and it is 65 nm in the reference sample.

3.3. Thermal decomposition of composites

3.3.1. Thermogravimetric analysis

The XRD results show that synthesis of composites of different CuHT:Zeolite ratio is possible and does not influence the structure of support. However, for understanding of thermal decomposition of CuHT:zeolite composites, we decided to study the selected structures: CuHT:ZSM_2:1, CuHT:ZSM(p)_2:1 and the reference zeolites by thermogravimetric analysis (Fig. 3). For the composite materials, additional MS measurements were also performed to show the gas evolution during the thermal decomposition process.

The ZSM(p) sample (Fig. 3B) shows the occurrence of only one minimum at DTG curve around 105 °C, what is connected to the release of free water [44,45]. The registered change of mass is 3 wt. %, while total change of mass is 4 wt. %. On the other hand, the DTG curve of ZSM (Fig. 3A) is more complex and shows three main steps of mass loss. The first step with DTG minimum at 70 and 190 °C is related to the water release, the second one (430 °C) is related to the removal of organic templates, while the last one (800 °C) is attributed to the dehydration and condensation of silicon hydroxyl groups in zeolite crystal [44,45]. Total weight loss for sample ZSM is 13 wt. %. Comparison of results registered up to 200 °C for both samples allows to assume that the ZSM material retains more water due to the hydrophilic nature, which is associated with the presence of Brønsted acid sites from aluminium in framework (see NH₃-TPD, Fig. 1). In contrast, the ZSM(p) sample seems to be more hydrophobic, what is related to the lower water adsorption (lower weight loss in the region up to 200 °C). The total weight loss might also suggest that the ZSM(p) has better thermal stability, with minimal weight loss at high temperatures.

The thermogravimetric curves of composite materials show that the change of mass for both samples is significantly higher in comparison to the reference materials, 34 wt. % for CuHT-ZSM_2:1 and 30 wt. % for CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1. The higher change of mass is related to the thermal decomposition of hydrotalcite-like compounds deposited over the zeolite surface during the synthesis process. The character of TG curves compared with the MS (mass spectrometry) signals (Fig. 3) allows to observe the three main stages of thermal decomposition. The first stage (I) is related to the removal of water adsorbed on the outer surface of sample (130 °C) and decomposition of carbonates located at samples surface (CO₂ signal, 110 °C and 140 °C). The second stage of decomposition process (II) is related to the decomposition of interlayer water molecules (225 and 200 °C). Additionally, for sample CuHT-ZSM_2:1 the small signal of CO₂ release at 235 °C is observed. The last stage of mass loss (III) connects signals ascribed to the decomposition of interlayer CO₃²⁻ anions (CO₂ signals), and to the decomposition of brucite-like

layers (H₂O signals). Occurrence of two peaks related to water at 350 or 330 °C and at 420 or 390 °C, indicated presence of the OH⁻ anions of different stability [11,41,46]. According to Taguchi et al. [47] and Li et al. [48], the decomposition of hydroxyl groups of Al(OH)₃ and Mg(OH)₂ occurs at 295 °C and 377 °C, respectively. Therefore, since our hydrotalcite layers contain both type of cations, the occurrence of two peaks for H₂O release at the MS spectra suggests the release of OH⁻ anions bound to Al (lower temperatures) and Mg (higher temperatures). Analysis of the CO₂ signal also shows occurrence of species of different stability, that is probably influenced by the presence of Al³⁺ and Mg²⁺ cations [11].

The character of TG-MS curve seems to be similar to the profiles of previously studied Cu-Mg-Al materials [11,41] as well as the hydrotalcites of different chemical composition [39,49,50]. The observation suggests that the deposition of HT over the zeolite support did not result in changes in the thermal decomposition of HT precursor.

3.3.2. Structural transformation with temperature

The XRD patterns shown in Fig. S2 (Supplementary) illustrate the thermal decomposition of materials at various calcination temperatures. Zeolite phase is clearly observable up to 900 °C for CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1 and up to 800 °C for CuHT-ZSM_2:1. Although the positions of the ZSM-5 diffraction peaks remain unchanged, indicating preservation of the zeolite framework, a slight decrease in crystallinity is observed for the calcined samples compared to the non-calcined ones. This decrease is relatively minor at lower calcination temperatures, while a pronounced loss of crystallinity becomes evident only at 800 °C for CuHT-ZSM_2:1 and at 900 °C for CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1.

The hydrotalcite structure is observed only up to 300 °C (blue region in Fig. S2, Supplementary). The presence of HT characteristic peaks at 200 °C stays in line with the results of TG-MS data, confirming that the release of H₂O at 130 °C is related to surface water, while the signal above 200 °C is related to decomposition of interlayers anion and further dehydroxylation of layered structure (Fig. 3). The increase of calcination temperature results in formation of oxides with different structure. The periclase (MgO) is visible in the diffractograms at 400 °C and above, at 50 and 74 °2 Theta (ICCD Pdf-2 card no. 00-004-0829). The MgO is the only oxide that is detected with XRD up to 800 °C. For both studied materials, the spinel like phase ([Cu,Mg]Al₂O₄) is observed at samples calcined at 900 °C (ICCD Pdf-2 card no. 01-075-4035). For sample CuHT-ZSM_2:1, the additional peaks that correspond to the clinostatite (MgSiO₃) are visible at 33 and 41 °2 Theta (ICCD Pdf-2 card no. 00-035-0610).

The characteristic peaks for CuO are not observed at any temperature, despite the fact that copper is introduced in the synthesis step. Previously, we observed similar effect for the mixed metal oxides materials formed after the calcination of HT. For materials with low Cu mol. % loading, the CuO was not observed at the diffractograms. However, the presence of CuO phase was confirmed by other methods (H₂-TPR),

Fig. 2. The XRD patterns of composite materials.

Fig. 3. Results of thermogravimetric studies combined with MS analysis of released gases, A. ZSM and CuHT-ZSM_2:1; B. ZSM(p) and CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1.

suggesting that the crystallite size is below the XRD detection or the copper oxides are partially amorphous [8–10,12].

3.3.3. Surface area and porosity evolution

The textural properties of samples calcined at different temperatures are summarized in Table 2. The adsorption-desorption isotherms, together with the pore size distribution plots are presented in Fig. S3–S5 (Supplementary). The analysis of isotherms shows that despite the chemical composition or calcination temperature, materials exhibit the type IV of isotherms with the hysteresis loop type H4, characteristic for micro-mesoporous materials [52,53].

Given that the prepared materials are composite systems consisting of a zeolite framework combined with hydrotalcite and hydrotalcite-derived mixed oxides, the selection of a single, unequivocal strategy for the evaluation of physisorption data is inherently non-trivial.

Table 2

Textural properties of CuHT-ZSM_2:1 and CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1 calcined at different temperature and reference zeolite materials.

CuHT-ZSM_2:1					CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1				
T (°C)	$S_{BET}^{[a]/[b]}$ (m ² /g)	$Ext_{SA}^{[c]}$ (m ² /g)	$V_{NET}^{[d]}$ (cm ³ /g)	MV ^[e] (mm ³ /g)	T (°C)	$S_{BET}^{[a]/[b]}$ (m ² /g)	$Ext_{SA}^{[c]}$ (m ² /g)	$V_{NET}^{[d]}$ (cm ³ /g)	MV ^[e] (mm ³ /g)
20	138/149	80	219	28	20	265/269	239	416	12
200	144/160	76	248	33	200	277/280	234	482	20
300	146/166	75	249	36	300	277/280	211	462	32
400	235/251	91	244	68	400	335/334	232	472	50
500	216/233	67	181	71	500	305/306	185	411	59
600	270/282	98	286	81	600	306/303	164	405	67
700	261/275	79	230	86	700	300/301	163	400	67
800	203/207	89	236	53	800	284/281	151	371	62
900	112/112	99	255	5	900	220/222	126	332	46

ZSM				ZSM(p)					
T (°C)	$S_{BET}^{[a]/[b]}$ (m ² /g)	$Ext_{SA}^{[c]}$ (m ² /g)	$V_{NET}^{[d]}$ (cm ³ /g)	MV ^[e] (mm ³ /g)	T (°C)	$S_{BET}^{[a]/[b]}$ (m ² /g)	$Ext_{SA}^{[c]}$ (m ² /g)	$V_{NET}^{[d]}$ (cm ³ /g)	MV ^[e] (mm ³ /g)
20	256/261	48	102	86	20	343/370	88	167	130

[a] S_{BET} – evaluated based on the standard BET equation.

[b] S_{BET} – evaluated based on the modified Rouqueler BET equation.

[c] Ext_{SA} – external surface area.

[d] V_{NET} – total pore volume.

[e] MV – micropore volume.

Therefore, surface area and porosity characteristics were assessed using more than one approach. The BET surface area was determined using the conventional methodology, while an additional modified BET evaluation, better suited for microporous materials, was also applied.

It should be noted that it is expected that hydrotalcite does not form within the zeolite micropores due to structural restrictions. Consequently, upon calcination, the resulting mixed metal oxide phase is expected to be located predominantly on the external surface of the zeolite particles, which is also where the catalytically active Cu-oxide species should be situated.

At the same time, parameters derived from the modified BET analysis and the micropore volume in combination with total pore volume, provide valuable information on the structural evolution of the composite system. These values reflect changes in the microporous framework of the zeolite and thus offer insight into the structural integrity and stability of the zeolite carrier during composite formation and subsequent thermal treatment.

The determined specific surface area of as synthesized CuHT-ZSM_2:1 and CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1 is 138 and 265 m²/g, respectively. The deposition of the hydrotalcite phase onto the zeolite support led to a pronounced decrease in the BET specific surface area, which can be attributed to partial blockage of the zeolite micropores. Conversely, the incorporation of the HT phase resulted in an increase in the external surface area and total pore volume, indicating that these textural properties are predominantly contributed by the HT phase itself. The calcination of the material at 200 and 300 °C caused only very slight increase of surface area, since the hydrotalcite decomposition is not yet finished as confirmed by the XRD analysis. Further increase of calcination temperature to 400 °C resulted in increase of S_{BET} to 235 and 335 m²/g for CuHT-ZSM_2:1 and CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1, respectively. The increase of surface area is related to the decomposition of HT layers and formation of MgO (Fig. 4). For sample CuHT-ZSM_2:1(p), further calcination to 700 °C does not affect the surface area while above 700 °C results in a decrease of S_{BET} from 300 to 220 m²/g at 900 °C. On the other hand, for CuHT-ZSM_2:1 the progressive increase of surface area is observed up to 600 °C followed by a decrease of S_{BET} to 112 m²/g at 900 °C. Similar trends can be observed for surface area if evaluated by modified approach.

The external surface area (Ext_{SA}) and micropore volume (MV) were evaluated based on the t-plot analysis. The observed values of Ext_{SA} are different for both set of samples: markedly higher external surface was obtained for CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1 and its value slightly decreased with increasing calcination temperature, while for CuHT-ZSM_2:1 it does not

Fig. 4. The surface area and crystallite size as a function of temperature **A.** CuHT-ZSM_2:1 and **B.** CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1. The crystallite sizes were calculated based on XRD patterns.

change. The evolution of the micropore volume shows that calcination up to 700 °C is accompanied by a progressive increase in apparent microporosity. This behaviour can be attributed to thermally induced transformations of the hydrotalcite phase deposited on the zeolite surface, which initially limits the accessibility of the zeolite microporous network. Upon calcination, hydrotalcite decomposes into mixed oxides, leading to gradual unblocking of the zeolite micropores and an increase in the measured micropore volume. In contrast, the total pore volume

increases only up to 400 °C and subsequently decreases with further temperature increase. This trend corresponds to the temperature range in which hydrotalcite is fully decomposed into mixed oxides, followed by their progressive crystallization and sintering at higher temperatures, resulting in a reduction of surface area and total pore volume. At calcination temperatures of 800–900 °C, a pronounced decrease in micropore volume is observed, which can be associated with partial degradation of the zeolite framework and the consequent loss of structural integrity of the microporous network. Moreover, the diffractogram of CuHT-ZSM_2:1 (900 °C), shows occurrence of an additional phase: clinoenstatite (MgSiO_3). According to Jin et al. [51], the MgSiO_3 can be obtained at temperature around 800 °C, while the increase of temperature increases the crystallinity. Thus, observed clinoenstatite might be the result of an *in-situ* thermal synthesis from decomposed silica frame of zeolites and the magnesium from HT precursor.

Overall, the deposition of hydrotalcite onto the zeolite leads to a marked reduction in surface area and micropore volume due to restricted pore accessibility, while subsequent thermal decomposition temporarily enhances surface-related parameters through oxide formation. The zeolite framework remains largely preserved after the initial modification up to approximately 800 °C, above which framework collapse and micropore loss become evident, in good agreement with the XRD results.

3.4. Characterisation of calcined composites

3.4.1. Morphology analysis of calcined materials

The SEM micrographs of CuHT-ZMS 2:1 (Fig. 5) were made for the non-calcined materials (NC) and for those calcined at 500, 700 and 900 °C. The image of NC sample does not show formation of any specific structure. The sample is composed from the aggregates of different shape and size. On the other hand, the samples calcined at 500 °C show the formation of plates/needles that are stacked together. The plates are spread uniformly at the samples surface. Increase of calcination temperature resulted in change of samples morphology. The plate-like structures are still easily to recognize; however, the formation of big aggregates (vs samples calcined at 500 °C) is also observable.

For sample CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1, the SEM micrographs of as synthesized material (NC) also do not show formation of specific particles. The micrographs of calcined materials (Fig. 6) reveal occurrence of the aggregates of different size and shape (marked yellow). Sample calcination at 500 °C results in the formation of large stacked aggregates (marked yellow) that grow with the temperature increase. The small plate like particles, similar like for sample CuHT-ZSM_2:1 are not observed. The

Fig. 5. The SEM microstructures of sample CuHT-ZSM_2:1: as synthesized (NC) and calcined at 500, 700 and 900 °C.

CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1

Fig. 6. The SEM microstructures of sample CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1: as synthesized (NC) and calcined at 500, 700 and 900 °C.

similar plate-like particles that are observed at 500 and 700 °C are different and aggregated in random places (marked white).

The EDS maps of elements distribution (Fig. S6 and Fig. S7) show that the copper is homogeneously dispersed over the samples surface, without formation of any visible aggregates, despite the calcination temperature.

3.4.2. Reducibility of Cu species

The reduction profiles of samples calcined at 400, 600 and 800 °C

Fig. 7. The reduction profiles of samples CuHT-ZSM_2:1 and CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1 calcined at 400, 600 and 800 °C.

(Fig. 7) show occurrence of a wide reduction peak with the maximum at about 400 °C, that can be ascribed to reduction of Cu-species. The position of the maximum slightly changes with increase of calcination temperature suggesting formation of Cu-species of different reducibility. The change of reducibility might be associated with the change of the crystallite size, formation of different type of Cu species or with interactions of copper MgAl spinel species as well as with zeolite support.

So far, we studied the Cu-containing mixed metal oxides obtained by calcination of hydrotalcites, where the H₂-TPR maxima ascribed to Cu²⁺ → Cu⁰ reduction of copper in dispersed and bulk-like CuO form were registered at 250–300 °C, while the possible additional peaks at higher temperatures were assigned to the spinel like phases [9–12]. For Cu supported samples with low copper loadings, the shift of the reduction peak to temperatures above 350 °C was published and was explained by hindered reduction of isolated Cu²⁺ ions strongly interacting with the support possibly even forming nonstoichiometric surface copper aluminates [54]. Hindered reduction might be also explained as be the result of strong metal-support interactions (SMSI). Qi et al. [55] reported that the SMSI can be manifested by different aspects, as the improvement of stability of supported metal. Thus, the Cu reduction peak above 400 °C can be attributed to strong metal-support interaction that stabilize Cu species, making them more difficult to be reduced.

Contrary to oxide species, where reduction typically proceeds as one-step reduction, exchanged copper species in zeolites represents a two-step process [56] via Cu⁺ as a stable intermediate [57]. If sample contains all kind of Cu species (oxides and zeolite exchanges species), very complex profile is obtained. In our case there is only one peak typical for CuO in highly dispersed amorphous-like form, which is in accordance with XRD results. Unlike the TPR of bulk copper oxides, the reduction of Cu²⁺ ions exchanged into zeolites should not produce water, as protons generated during H₂ activation are retained by the zeolite framework as Brønsted acid sites. Since water formation simultaneously to H₂ consumption was observed during additional TPR without cold-trap and on-line connected quadrupole MS (not shown), the Cu deposited on zeolite support must be in our case predominantly in the oxide form. The obtained results also show that the Si/Al ratio do not influence the samples reducibility as is expected for oxide form of Cu species, while for zeolite exchanges species, the reducibility of the Cu ions increased with the decreasing concentration of Al in the framework [57].

Besides main peak, a shoulder at high-temperature side indicating additional possible peak is observed. It was confirmed by quadrupole MS detection, that this is the artefact of TCD detector, due to release of residual CO₂ and CO obtained by its reduction.

3.4.3. Acidic properties of calcined composites

The NH₃-TPD profiles (Fig. 8), show two main overlapping peaks. Similar to the fresh samples, the peaks at around 200–250 °C correspond to low-temperature desorption, while the second peak around 400–450 °C is associated with the high temperature desorption [40]. However, despite the presence of similar peak maxima, a comparison of the profiles for fresh, unmodified ZSM-5 supports and the modified materials (Fig. 8) reveals significant changes in the desorption patterns and in the total amount of desorbed NH₃.

It is evident that in the case of the CuHT-ZSM_2:1 sample, addition of hydrotalcite and calcination lead to a reduction of the acidity if compared with the fresh (and even hydrothermally treated) material. On the other hand, for sample Cu-ZSM(p)_2:1, the opposite trend is observed: the introduction of hydrotalcite and further calcination enhances the material acidity, likely due to the formation of new Lewis sites from Cu²⁺ and Mg²⁺ species [58].

A comparison of samples calcined at different temperatures shows that increasing the calcination temperature results in decrease in total desorbed NH₃ (Fig. 8). Additionally, NH₃ desorption for samples CuHT-ZSM_2:1 is higher than for samples CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1. Similar trend was observed for the fresh ZSM and ZSM(p) samples. This suggests that acidity is closely linked to the presence of aluminium in the phase

Fig. 8. The NH₃-TPD measurements of A. CuHT-ZSM_2:1 and B. CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1 composites.

composition. The parent hydrotalcite material (CuHT) that we intended to deposit over the zeolite support contains approx. 30 mol.% of Al (Cu + Mg + Al = 100 mol.%). Therefore, in case of the ZSM(p) support, thus pure Si material, the increased acidity is due to the introduction of CuHT phase and its contribution to Lewis acidity.

At the same time, the decrease in total desorbed NH₃ and the diminishing intensity of both low- and high-temperature desorption peaks in both sets of samples with increasing calcination temperature can be attributed to the loss of Brønsted acid sites, possibly due to framework dealumination in Al-containing ZSM support and thermal decomposition of CuHT species in ZSM(p). Furthermore, peak broadening and slight shifts in temperature maxima suggest modifications in the strength of remaining acid sites, particularly in CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1, where new Lewis acid sites might emerge.

3.5. Catalytic results

Our concept was to combine zeolites as supports with hydrotalcites as precursors of the active phase in order to obtain catalysts with high surface area and well-dispersed active sites. Since this article focuses primarily on material aspects, we emphasised how synthesis and post-synthesis treatment influence the formation of stable HT-zeolite and MMO-zeolite structures that meet our assumptions—namely achieving well-dispersed Cu species while preserving high surface area without collapse of the zeolite framework. These findings provide a foundation for our ongoing work, where optimisation of Cu loading, dispersion, and other catalytic parameters will be systematically addressed.

For the purposes of this study, catalytic performance is demonstrated

on a single representative sample CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1_600 (the material calcined at 600 °C). The NH₃-SCO tests presented here (Fig. 9) serve as an illustrative example of the catalytic behaviour of the MMO–zeolite system. The CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1_600 catalyst shows markedly higher conversion compared with counterpart material prepared without zeolite support presented in Ref. [10]: 88 % NH₃ conversion versus 28 % NH₃ conversion with 95 % selectivity to N₂ in both cases, indicating clear potential for further optimisation of this approach. However, owing to the compositional flexibility of hydrotalcite precursors and the broad variability of zeolite supports, such MMO–zeolite catalysts have the potential for application in a wide range of catalytic processes.

4. Conclusion

The aim of our research was to synthesize Cu-containing hydrotalcite (CuHT) supported on ZSM-5 zeolites of different Si/Al ration and provide valuable insights into the one-pot synthesis of these materials. The idea of this research comes from our previous studies when we investigated the CuHT materials as precursors of catalysts used in selective catalytic ammonia oxidation. Those studies [10,12] highlighted the importance of CuO dispersion and its availability on the catalysts surface. Based on these findings, it is expected that synthesis of the CuHT-zeolite composites and subsequent *in situ* transformation of CuHT into mixed metal oxides should result in formation of materials with highly dispersed oxide forms with high availability, i.e., dispersed on high surface area.

The results confirm that the synthesis of composite is possible under the standard conditions of hydrotalcite synthesis (pH = 10, T = 60–65 °C). Simultaneously, no decomposition or ZSM-5 framework integrity was observed. The position of characteristic XRD peaks, as well as the ZSM-5 crystallite size does not change with the time of hydrothermal treatment. However, the analysis of NH₃-TPD (Fig. 1) shows that the hydrothermal treatment results in a change of the ZSM-5 (Si/Al = 11.5) acidity affecting both low- and high-temperature acid sites, while the 100 % Si samples show the similar TPD-profile and the similar amount of NH₃ desorbed. Since the XRD confirms no framework collapse, the changes of acid sites observed for ZSM-5 (Si/Al = 11.5) are related to the partial dealumination or leaching of aluminium atoms from the framework. The initial presence of aluminium creates the Brønsted acid sites [59], that are converted into weak or non-acidic sites due to the removal of Al atoms. Hypothesis that the change of acidity is related to the Al presence rather than to the framework degradation is also confirmed by comparison of the results for ZSM and ZSM(p) samples.

The XRD measurements of as-synthesized materials confirm formation of hydrotalcite-like materials on the ZSM-5 supports. The subsequent thermal treatment of compounds resulted in an *in-situ* transformation of hydrotalcites into mixed metal oxides (MMO), while zeolite supports show high stability up to 800 °C. The analysis of TG-MS profiles registered for chosen samples shows that the evolution of gases is similar to that obtained for the pure hydrotalcite structure [11,39,43,60], it means that thermal decomposition of hydrotalcites over the surface of zeolites is not influenced by the support. However, at the same time the XRD results do not confirm the formation of the CuO particles, that were expected, due to the chemical composition of precursors. The lack of copper oxides can be explained by the low crystallinity of CuO (below the detection limit of XRD), which was confirmed by TPR-H₂ experiments as well as EDS mapping.

Textural characterization revealed that the optimal calcination temperature for achieving the highest specific surface area (S_{BET}) and porosity is in the range of 500–600 °C. Higher temperatures led to progressive loss of surface area due to increased crystallinity and pore collapse, with partial transformation of zeolite into MgSiO₃ observed at 900 °C.

The findings of this study highlight the potential of CuHT-ZSM-5 composites as promising catalytic materials, particularly for NH₃-SCO

Fig. 9. Catalytic results for CuHT-ZSM(p)_2:1_600.

applications. Future research should focus on evaluating their catalytic activity under real reaction conditions, as well as exploring the long-term stability and resistance to poisoning by H₂O. Additionally, the approach developed here could be extended to other zeolite structures to further tailor material properties for specific catalytic applications.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sylwia Górecka: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Katerina Pacultová:** Writing – review & editing. **Katerina Karásková:** Investigation. **Kamil Górecki:** Investigation. **Katerina Kupková:** Investigation. **Eva Kinnertová:** Methodology, Investigation. **Antonio Eduardo Palomares Gimeno:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Lucie Obalová:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2026.114031>.

Data availability

Data are available in repository Zenodo
[Novel hydrotalcite-zeolite composites as precursors for catalysis: Synthesis, transformation and structural stability \(Original data\)](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.15111111)

(Zenodo)

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